

Journal of Economics and Business

Sakaya, Ansgar J. (2020), Emancipation of Workers' and Management Thoughts for Leveraging Performance in the Public Sector. In: *Journal of Economics and Business*, Vol.3, No.2, 507-523.

ISSN 2615-3726

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.03.02.216

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Economics and Business* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Journal of Economics and Business* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Economics and Business, which includes, but not limited to, Business Economics (Micro and Macro), Finance, Management, Marketing, Business Law, Entrepreneurship, Behavioral and Health Economics, Government Taxation and Regulations, Financial Markets, International Economics, Investment, and Economic Development. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Economics and Business* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Economics and Business.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Emancipation of Workers' and Management Thoughts for Leveraging Performance in the Public Sector

Ansgar J. Sakaya¹

¹Department of Business Studies, Mzumbe University, Tanzania, P.O. Box 6559 Mbeya, Email: ansgar.sakaya@gmail.com

Abstract

The study aimed at examining the role of Job Security in influencing workers' Performance in the Public Sector. Data were gathered through survey questionnaire from sample of 60 workers at Tandahimba district Council Head quarter in Tanzania. Sampling strategies used were stratified and simple random sampling. Data were analysed quantitatively through descriptive statistics-compare means, ANOVA, t-test, Kruskal-Wallis test and Factors analysis. Findings indicate that, significant differences exist between workers and their demographic characteristics towards job performance and job security; moreover, they also account for a portion of their performance problems. Persistence of performance problems in the public sector has been attributed to Governance factors like proficiency problems of line-managers. Behaviour factors of workers like poor attitude towards the employer, public funds and properties. Economic factors like workers' over-dependence on the government. The study recommends people in management levels in the public sector of Tanzania to embark on proper strategic management practices as all best practices for managing workers and their performance have already been laid down; the issue is how to use them strategically for better outcomes of workers and the government excellence. Helping Public workers to understand that, they are expected to be more patriotic in serving the public interest, act in due diligence in protecting public properties and funds, continue insisting public workers on the role of self-values and integrity in public service as it will help them couple with complex work conditions.

Keywords: Workers, Job Performance, Job Security, Public Sector, Tanzania

1. An overview

Governments all over the world are struggling to achieve their set strategic plans objectives like technological advancement that would have helped them accomplish parts of their set goals, the bad thing is, they have rarely been concerned with workers' problems that would have resolved critical issues of unsatisfactory performance. If one goes deeper into understanding workers' performance problems you will realize that, they are taken as HR concerns only rather than leaders or operations managers (Risher and Wilder, 2018). Workers' performance has been deterred by many critical factors and among them is Job security which is necessary for influencing performance. It is vital for the management of any organization to know how best to secure their workers' jobs to leveraging performance. Persistent excellences in job performance depend on how the organization handles matters associated with job security and performances of their esteemed workers (Lucky et al., 2013; Ahmed et al., 2016). Workers in any organization should work under favourable environment which can assist to get job

security together with enhanced performance. Organizations which have clear work policy for securing workers from vulnerable work issues are in better position to motivate workers towards increased performance because workers have no stress and fear (Gupta, 2016; Jimenez and Didona 2017), stress and fear among workers and management members are associated with problems of not meeting closing date, underestimating budget, evade decisions making, hiding problems, loss of moral and not being resourceful to the organization (Haenisch, 2012), these problems are found with public workers of which are attributed by ways people are brought up and the leadership systems. Job security has positive aspect of workers' career growth which ultimately fosters performance. Of course, the problem of job security right now is faced by both private and public sectors due to changes taking place within the government. Job security has greater impact also on workers' behaviour towards the job and management, never the less, job security signifies employer's commitment to workers and vice versa is true (Ahmed et al., 2016). Absence of job security means the absence of good management practices and the presence of job security means, the employer is ready to invest to its workers for excelling towards achieving its strategic goals (Moon, 2001).

It has been noted that, there has been an unsatisfactory performance of public workers for some time despite then efforts undertaken. Current changes in the public sector demand performance culture, good values and integrity. Despite the changes and effort taken by the current government, still, some unsatisfactory performance persists silently among workers in various areas which now calls for the emancipation of public workers and management thoughts with regards to job security in relation to job performance. Emancipation is highly needed as it is not well understood as to why people employed in public sector are not motivated to perform at optimal levels despite of guaranteed job security. Of course, job security alone is not enough to guarantee workers' performance. Job security is believed to be the gratification attained by workers from their work which in turn bestows all the effort for their organization excellence (Baker & Abou-Ismael, 1993), you may ask yourself a question; if the attained gratification is due to job security, then, why they do not perform? Or why they have poor attitude towards public properties and funds? This is an indicator that, some workers have problems. The government has shouted over the problem of unsatisfactory performance but still the problem does exist silently. Yes, there is contradictory information with regard to how job security and workers' performance are related (Ojedokun, 2008).

1.1 Study Objective and Hypotheses

To find out the difference of age, gender, marital statuses and education with job performance in public sector

1.1.1 Hypotheses covering the study

H₀₁:Governance factors have no relationship with workers' performance

H₀₂:Economic factors have no association with workers' performance

H₀₃:Behaviour factors have no association with workers' performance

H₀₄:Demographic factors of (ages, gender and marital statuses) have no association with workers' performance and job security

H₀₅:Public sector workers' education has no association with their performance and job security

1.2 Expectations of the study

It is expected to assist management in various government institutions and parastatals that, job security alone is not enough to motivate workers towards optimal performance; rather, there are critical factors like leadership and good management practices like those advanced in Deming's 14 points and Kaizen that could help tackle performance problems in the public sector, but also, it will help workers open up their minds by having positive attitudes towards the government, its properties and funds.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Performance problems and Work Security

It is essential for management to know the status of balance between workers' success and organization success. If there is an imbalance of the two we expect performance to be low and hence poor output. Organizations have to keep in mind that, workers are individuals with their own set of demands and have certain goals to be fulfilled for reaching peaks of their career ladder. If workers do not find any career growth, his/her feeling towards performance will drop significantly. Job performance is the yield expected from a worker that is associated with the overall strategic goals of the organization (Cascio, 2006). Evidence shows that, the major problems of poor performance are accounted by poor administration, unexpected pitiable management practices like organization injustice, inappropriate performance evaluation process, conflicting management interests, working culture problems like failure to associate management strategies and the prevailing culture and the nature of the workforce in operations, leadership problems which are critical for satisfactory performance, fear in making decisions, political inclusion in public service provision (Sverke, et al., 2006; Katzenbach et al., 2012), economic problems, venality acts, unhealthy work life-balance, no counselling on workers' life, presence of gossiping or making decisions based on grapevine, despising lower level workers, personal family issues, underutilisation of Deming's 14 points in workers management and other poor human resource practices that ultimately upshot for poor performance in public sector (Walton, 1986; Longenecker and Iffakis, 2002; St. Charles County Business Record, 2005; Haenisch, 2012). Workers' output that is due to performance is accounted by gratification derived from various job factors and one of it is job security, so, worker's output signifies his/her attitude towards the organization is working for (Imran et al., 2015). Work security is a status quo of worker's mind that, the job status will persist for quite a time (Jandaghi et al., 2011). Organizations which have good status of job security with good policy and clear rules and regulations have more chance to retain workers than those with low level of job security (Simon, 2011; Khan, 2014).

Designing work conditions responsive to external variations, gratifying workers, sustaining performance culture and evolving administrations system has become a challenge to many governments and has accounted for major performance problems. It is certainly true that, if you assess the working culture in most of public sector's offices are not good for leveraging workers' performance. Neither no managers or operations workers are concerned with performance culture; this is possibly due to how they are brought up from their families or the learning channels went through. The absence of hard working culture in public sector is costing the government enormously by placing a huge burden to recruitment secretariat in finding best performers. Presence of outstanding culture would have shaped workers attitudes towards hard working (Hai Li et al., 2011). This phenomenon has even brought problems not only to performance output but even in the area of attitude towards public funds and properties. It can be seen that, most people appointed to different posts in public sector have been replaced from their post and even several boards from various governmental parastatals and institutions been dissolved due to integrity, values and performance problems. Questions may be raised up concerning performance of public workers in relation to working culture, but possibly there is an untapped answer as Abdullah, et al., (2013) says, the problem of poor performance has been looked by many practitioners from a narrow angle and they have forgotten important factors that may account to other performance problems which may be personal characters mismatch with post or the organization culture or team members or practices (Hough & Connelly, 2013).

2.2 Differentiating workers

Individuals do not only differ in their mental and physical make up, rather, they also differ in their psychological aspects. Each individual is unique and has unique contribution, therefore, management have to deal with each individual distinctly to get their best contribution. It is very difficult for employers to understand the difference of their workers under normal circumstances; exception comes if they take into account of workers' attitude towards the job. This is so because; workers may have similar technical skills but differs in behaviour skills (Albino, 2018). Individual attitude is based on favourable or unfavourable assessment towards an idea or the object (Blackwell et al., 2001; Garcia-Santillan et al., 2012). Favorable workers' attitude would lead to positive response to changes undertaken while unfavourable attitudes lead to the opposite (Gupta, 2016). Workers have to be tuned to survive even in adverse circumstances, living in mental state of readiness to constant changes; bad luck, managers have failed to build organizational capability to help their workers couple with adverse circumstances. Leadership has a great role in leveraging workers' performance by taking into account of their

personality factor. Poor organizations may complain about workers' performance but smart organization may start by looking at the fit between workers and the leadership because it has a serious influence towards workers' performance as behavior elicited by leaders regardless of the position will make supervisee behave or do the same (Longenecker and Leffakis, 2002; Khan et al., 2014).

2.3 Demographic factors in association with job security and performance

Demographic characteristics of workers determine their performance and attitude towards job security over their work lifetime, aging variation has great influence on work performance abilities on task demands (Darwin, 2014; Timar, 2014). Job security is also associated to worker's age, workers with small age do not put much consideration on job security as they can find jobs easily as compared to the aged people who are no longer mobile and therefore, they consider job security positively (Salladarr'e et al., 2010). Gender is also believed to impact workers' performance but will also vary with the nature of the task at hand (Jimoh, 2008; Stone et al., 2016), other studies found no association of gender with job security while others have found, females are more prone to job security than men due to family matters like handling children, men are more mobile (Hakim, 1996). Job performance also varies with Marital statuses, some studies show that, married people have good job performance as compared to unmarried one and other studies got the opposite of the facts (Khurshid, Qasmi and Ashuraf, 2012; Lekha and Magesh, 2016) and some found no difference of marital statuses on job performance (Salladarr'e et al., 2010; Omori and Basse, 2019), as well as no association of marital statuses and job security (Salladarr'e et al., 2010). Moreover, workers' education assists in acquiring various job proficiencies that helps workers perform their job duties as opposed to the one who does not have relevant education (Thomas and Feldman, 2009), but it is not guaranteed for educated workers to always be good performers (Frese, 2002). Salladarr'e et al., (2010) found no association of workers' education and job security as they do not see it as a motivational factor when looking for jobs, what is important is payment, those with tertiary levels of education have positive feelings towards job security but is been destructed by entrance of educated workers over time (Salladarr'e et al., 2010).

2.4 Economic condition of the Country in relation to Job Security

The country's economic status has a great role in fostering workers' wellbeing in public sector as it was noticed before; leadership is a critical factor in fostering performance in all sectors of the country. Better economic wellbeing of the country is also translated from good workers' performance and to good workers' welfares like good financial and nonfinancial rewards including job security (Noraishah et al., 2017). Unhealthy economy makes public workers lose confidence and therefore, is translated in terms of workers' healthy challenges, poor performance, Job insecurity, bribery and political challenges (Sverke, et al., 2006; Şenol, 2014; Shah et al., 2015; Awadh et al., 2015).

2.5 Motivation and workers' performance

Motivation is the energy that triggers a person to act in manner that can be favourable or unfavourable. It can also be referred as the intensity, persistence and direction of the efforts put forth in achieving organizational goals (Armstrong, 2006). Job performance can be achieved by means of pushing, directing and persuading workers. It is surprising nowadays, public workers only put in minimum effort towards job performance since they have no public interest, and the only purpose of doing job is to serve the basic needs of their families. A question that people need to think of is why public workers have lower interest and motives in rendering good service, caring of public properties and funds? The answer can be that, management responsible for supervising the daily operations have underutilised good management practices, nevertheless, leadership proficiency in this area is also deficient. Workers' motivation is mainly determined by work settings, firm's management procedures and personality traits of workers (Cardy, 2004; Nzuve and Mwangi, 2015). Motivating workers towards job performance is an art but also demands the science side for better outcomes. Each individual in the working place is unique and therefore calls for unique motivation mechanisms.

2.6 Theories guiding workers' motivation

2.6.1 Herzberg theory

Herzberg has identified two factors motivating workers; motivators and hygiene factors. For hygiene factors, a worker to feel that he/she is secured with the job need to have good working condition, good salary, good organization policies and management excellence. Absence of these factors will result to job insecurity; the second factor is motivators need and involves things like accomplishment, challenging job, growth, acknowledgment and responsibilities. This theory emphasises as to why people need to work hard and why work in that organization (Gibson, 2000; Huling, 2003).

2.6.2 Equity theory

There are treatment problems to workers arising from a number of factors; this theory put forward the idea of fairness and unfair practices by management. Equitable treatment of workers will make them be motivated for good performance, if they are treated inequitably they will become de-motivated and their working moral will diminish and tarnish out their performance effort. This theory urge management to pay attention to equitable treatment of their workers for best performance and output, workers are suffering much from inequitable treatment from their supervisors that is why, some of them are exhausted and have low performance because, when they compare their effort and effort of others used in relation to job output and rewards or treatment they find no relation and in turn discourages them (Beardwell, 2001).

2.6.3 Vroom's Expectancy Theory:

This theory argues that, workers are looking forward to see that, behaving in a certain way will ultimately result to valued outcomes. Workers have the tendency of asking themselves can I do it? This question originates from workers career development, if they find they cannot do it due to lack of knowledge and skills they may complain, but the immediate results is poor performance that influences low output, they may ask themselves again what will I get for doing it? This is the reward factor that drives performance (Nzuve and Njambi, 2015); any behaviour related to performance elicited by workers have to be rewarded instantly as the longer it takes to reward workers for their performance the higher the meaningless it becomes as a motivational factor for performance, sustainability of the working or performance culture has been hampered much by reward time factor in public sector. Nevertheless, how much a worker values the reward also matters, the more the rewards are valued the higher the satisfaction that creates superfluous effort and ending up obtaining organizational objectives (Anwar et al., 2011). Management is insisted that, timely and realistic performance enticements helps in energizing workers' behaviour and the way workers are regarded by an organization and the way they regard and act towards it will determine its achievements (Dexit, 2002).

2.6.4 McGregor Participation Theory

This theory has two outlooks concerning people with regards to work, which is theory X and Y. Theory X believes that, people have low determination, don't like work, escape obligations, and need closer supervision. People working with public sector vary in terms of behaviour, personalities, working culture, attitude towards public service and so on. These differences account to large portion of public sector workers falling under theory X; that is why, performance problems still exist. Moreover, more effort, creativity and other necessary mechanism from managements are needed for emancipating workers' thoughts towards job performance. Theory Y believes that, people are in demand of accountability, can work out for self-directions, and prefers working. However, a worker may share both characteristics of theory Y and X (Rao, 2010), surely, workers falling under this category are few and not easy to find many of them in one working place.

Figure 1: Theoretical structure of the study

3. Methodology

3.1 Research design

A survey was deployed for this case and sampling frame involved two groups, heads of departments and normal workers in operations drawn from a population of 73 workers at Tandahimba district council head quarter. Robbins (2008) says, population is composed of two groups namely target population and the accessible population. “Sample” can be defined as part of objects or anything drawn from big group for studying and testing it to acquire information required (Robbins, 2008). Size of the sample was found by Yamane’s formula of 1967 as,

$$n = N / [1 + N(e)^2] \tag{1}$$

Where n=sample size, N=population of the study e=estimated margin error of sample (95% confidence level or 5% precision level was assumed).

n=62/73(100)=84.93% of the respondent.

Table 3.1 Populationa distribution and Sampling strategy

Category	Number of Workers	84.93% of the respondents	Adjusted Sample Size	Sampling Strategy
Heads of Departments	6	5.07	5	Random
Operational Workers	67	56.90	57	Random
Total	73	61.97	62	

3.2 Sampling and data collection technique

Stratified and random sampling strategies were used in gathering of data. Primary data were gathered through questionnaire designed in five likert scale point while secondary data were obtained from journals and books. Questionnaire’s internal consistence was examined by Cronbach's Alpha and had a value of .845 from 13 items which is high and allows for further analysis (Cronbach, 1951; Taber, 2018).

4. Data examination and study arguments

Sarantakos (1998) says, data analysis allows the researcher to bring data together, assessing them and drawing conclusions from facts findings. Gathered data were examined in six steps put forward by Creswell (2005), such steps include organizing, interpretation, explore and doing data coding, explaining findings by creating models,

doing presentation and report findings and finally interpreting the meaning in order to make general understanding.

Table 4.1 Respondents' information

Age Group	Frequency	percentage		Education Level	Frequency	Percept
18-20	10	16.1		Tertiary Education	22	35.5
21-30	16	25.8				
31-40	15	24.2		Vocational Training	11	17.7
41-50	16	25.8		Colleges	15	24.2
51 above	5	8.1		University	14	22.6
Total	62	100		Total	62	100
Gender				Marital Statuses		
Male	40	64.5		Single	22	35.5
Female	21	33.9		Married	37	59.7
Total	62	100		Widow	3	4.8
				Total	62	100

Table 4.2 Correlations

		Job Performance	Governance factors	Economic factors	Behavior factors
Job Performance	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	62			
Governance factors	Pearson Correlation	.989**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	62	62		
Economic factors	Pearson Correlation	.970**	.979**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	62	62	62	
Behavior factors	Pearson Correlation	.959**	.946**	.920**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	62	62	62	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.2 shows independent and dependent variables are highly correlated and statistically significant at 0.01 level of significance, KMO results is .718 of sample acceptability of three variables and the significant of the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity 0.000 which is acceptable (Kaiser, 1974; Field, 2005). The score of four items in the correlation table is .686 from Cronbach Alpha test which is reasonable (Taber, 2018). Thus, Factor Analysis can be carried out.

Table 4.3 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.897	96.558	96.558	2.897	96.558	96.558
2	.086	2.858	99.416			
3	.018	.584	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

One factor was generated from 3 variables and it explains about 96.558% of the total variance of workers' job performance in public sector.

Table 4.4 Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component
	1
Governance factors	.992
Economic factors	.984
Behavior factors	.972

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

a. 1 component was extracted covering values higher than .5, small values were suppressed.

Table 4.5 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.985 ^a	.969	.969	1.19465	.969	1899.437	1	60	.000	1.806

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Security

b. Dependent Variable: Job Performance

R score in table 4.5 is 0.985 which denotes the existence of strong association of dependent and independent variables as it is very near to one. R Square value is 0.969=96.9%, meaning that, Job performance is described by 96.9% of Job security. The other 3.1% of the dependent variable is described by factors not included in this case. Durbin-Watson of Job performance is 1.806 falling between the significant values of $1.5 < d < 2.5$, hence, no first order linear autocorrelation of this case data.

Table 4.6 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2710.837	1	2710.837	1899.437	.000 ^b
	Residual	85.631	60	1.427		
	Total	2796.468	61			

a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Job Security

ANOVA output in table 4.6 shows the statistical significance of the multiple linear regression model ($F=1899.437, p<0.01$). So, this model is statistically significant.

Table 4.7 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.739	.303		2.439	.018		
	Governance factors	1.489	.028	.989	52.553	.000	1.000	1.000
	Economic factors	1.095	.033	.974	33.376	.000	1.000	1.000
	Behavior factors	.161	.038	.220	4.262	.000	.104	9.575

a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance

Table 4.7 relates $t_{arithmetic}$ found in Table with t_{table} under this case, the variable governance factors, economic factors and behaviour factors associates with Job performance due to fact that $t_{arithmetic} > t_{table}$. Multiple linear regression model equation is given as: $job\ performance = .739 + 1.489(\text{Governance factors}) + 1.095(\text{Economic factors}) + .161(\text{Behaviour factors}) + \epsilon$. Multicollinearity issue in the model was not found as the tolerance values ranges between .104-1.000 higher than 0.10, VIF value ranges between 1.00-9.575 which is less than 10. Thus, the H_{01} , H_{02} and H_{03} are rejected and the alternative hypotheses are accepted.

Table 4.8 Correlations

		Job Performance	Age	Gender	Education level	Marital statuses
Job Performance	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
	N	62				
Age	Pearson Correlation	.918**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000				
	N	62	62			
Gender	Pearson Correlation	.390**	.368**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.003			
	N	62	62	62		
Education level	Pearson Correlation	.913**	.944**	.299*	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.018		
	N	62	62	62	62	
Marital statuses	Pearson Correlation	.773**	.839**	.393**	.859**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.002	.000	
	N	62	62	62	62	62

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

In table 4.8 most of variables are correlated at .01 level of significant and one variable is significant at .05. So, the variables confirm that, they associate with job performance. The score of four items in the correlation table is .686 from Cronbach Alpha test which is also reasonable (Taber, 2018), while the KMO of the four factors is .728 which is adequate for factor analysis process (Kaiser, 1974; Field, 2005).

Table 4.9 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.954	73.838	73.838	2.954	73.838	73.838
2	.817	20.421	94.259			
3	.179	4.472	98.730			
4	.051	1.270	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

One factor was generated from 4 variables and it explains about 73.838% of total variance of workers' job performance in public sector.

Table 4.10 Component Matrix^a

	Component
	1
Age	.957
Education level	.951
Marital statuses	.932
Gender	.514

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

a.1 components was extracted covering values higher than .5, small values were suppressed.

Table 4.11 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.818 ^a	.670	.664	3.92328	.670	121.682	1	60	.000	1.687

a. Predictors: (Constant), Demographic Factors

b. Dependent Variable: Job Performance

R score from table 4.11 is 0.818 which signifies there been a strong association of independent and dependent variable and it is near to one. R Square value is 0.670=67%, indicating that, Job performance is described by 67% of demographic factors. The other 33% of dependent variable is described by factors not included in this case. Durbin-Watson of Job performance is 1.687 which falls between the significant values of $1.5 < d < 2.5$, hence, no first order linear autocorrelation of this case data.

Table 4.12 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1872.940	1	1872.940	121.682	.000 ^b
	Residual	923.528	60	15.392		
	Total	2796.468	61			

a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Demographic Factors

ANOVA output in table 4.12 shows the statistical significance of the multiple linear regression model ($F=121.940$, $p<0.01$). So, this model is statistically significant.

Table 4.13 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	3.883	1.065		3.645	.001		
	Age	5.108	.284	.918	17.975	.000	1.000	1.000
	Gender	.268	.134	.106	1.997	.051	.793	1.262
	Education level	4.386	.254	.913	17.281	.000	1.000	1.000
	Marital statuses	-1.762	1.161	-.146	-1.518	.135	.240	4.169

Table 4.13 relates $t_{arithmetic}$ found in Table with t_{table} under this case, the variable age and education level influences Job performance because $t_{arithmetic} > t_{table}$. The multiple linear regression equation is given as: job performance = $3.883 + 5.108(\text{age}) + 4.386(\text{education level}) + \epsilon$. Gender variable has no significant influence towards job performance as it's ($\beta = .268, t = 1.997, p > .05$), while the variable marital statuses have negative influence towards job performance and statistically not significant, its values are ($\beta = -1.762, t = -1.518, p > .05$). Multicollinearity issue in the model was not found as the tolerance values ranges between .240-1.00 which is more than .10, VIF value ranges between 1.000 - 4.169 which is less than 10.

The significant difference of demographic characteristics with regard to job performance and job security was tested for normality due to difference in nature of data distribution, data with more than two categories and bared normal distribution were tested by ANOVA, this test assists in knowing which group differs from other groups as compared to Kruskal-Wallis test (Sagepub, 2017; Ostertagora et al., 2017). Data falling in more than three categories and did not bare normal distribution nature were tested by Kruskal-Wallis for justification purposes, this technique provides information about the difference of the groups but, it does not say which group differs from other group, moreover, it is very possible to get two different outcomes from the test, one being significant and the other not being significant, under such conditions, Shapiro-Wilk results are encouraged due to its reliability (Ezspss, 2020). T-test was used for groups falling under two categories.

Table 4.14 Descriptive Statistics for job performance

Education Level	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Tertiary education	10	11.04165	.014434	11.00	16.50
Vocational training	11	13.4545	1.57249	12.00	17.00
College	15	19.8000	1.78085	17.00	22.00
University	14	27.7857	2.32639	23.00	31.00
Total	62	17.3710	6.77080	11.00	31.00

Table 4.15 ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2656.067	4	664.017	269.577	.000
Within Groups	140.401	57	2.463		
Total	2796.468	61			

Table 4.15 has significant score of .000 which is small than the required alpha .05, thus, the null H_{05} is rejected because there were significant differences between groups, $F(4, 57) = 269.577, p < .00$. Job performance for workers who have attained University or College education differed significantly with those who have Tertiary education and Vocational training.

Table 4.16 Kruskal-Wallis test statistics

Kruskal-Wallis	Job performance			Job Security		
	df	Chi-square	Sig.	df	Chi-square	Sig.
Marital Statues	2	46.857	.000	2	45.809	.000
Kruskal-Wallis	Job performance			Job Security		
	df	Chi-square	Sig.	df	Chi-square	Sig.
Education	4	58.497	.000	4	59.125	.000

Justifying the significance difference between Workers' marital statuses and education with Job performance and job security, the Kruskal-Wallis test was deployed as from table 4.16 where the difference of marital statuses with job performance is ($p=.000 < 0.05$) and with job security is ($p=.000 < 0.05$) so, the null H_{04} is not accepted. Similarly, the difference of education with Job performance and job security was found, the impact of education on job performance ($p=.000 < 0.05$) and education on job security ($p=.000 < 0.05$) therefore, the null H_{05} is not accepted respectively. Similar results on marital statuses are found in table 4.17 and 4.18 below. Results from table 4.14-4.16 are supported by Salladarr'e et al., 2010 and Omari & bassey, 2019 on the influence of marital statuses on job performance. The association of workers' education and job security together with job performance is supported by Frese, 2002; Thomas and Feldman, 2009; and Salladarr'e et al., 2010.

Table 4.17 Descriptive statistics for job performance

Marital Statuses	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Single	22	11.0455	.21320	11.00	12.00
Married	37	20.0541	5.57248	12.00	29.00
Widow	3	30.6667	.57735	30.00	31.00
Total	62	17.3710	6.77080	11.00	31.00

Table 4.18 ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1676.955	2	838.477	44.189	.000
Within Groups	1119.513	59	18.975		
Total	2796.468	61			

Table 4.18 has significant score of .000 small than the required alpha .05, thus, the null hypothesis H_{04} is rejected because significant differences exist, marital statuses, $F(2, 59)=44.189$, $p < .00$. Workers' Job performance differs significantly with their marital statuses as seen also from table 4.16. The difference is of course controversial with this regard (Salladarr'e et al., 2010).

Table 4.19 Group Statistics

	Respondents' gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Job Security	Male	40	9.1250	1.41761	.22414
	Female	21	20.9524	2.37647	.51859
Job Performance	Male	40	12.9500	2.78227	.43992
	Female	21	25.1905	3.66905	.80065

Table 4.20 Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Job Security	Equal variances assumed	20.220	.000	-24.373	59	.000	-11.82738	-12.79841	-10.85635
	Equal variances not assumed			-20.935	27.675	.000	-11.82738	-12.98525	-10.66951
Job performance	Equal variances assumed	6.738	.012	-14.599	59	.000	-12.24048	-13.91818	-10.56277
	Equal variances not assumed			-13.399	32.385	.000	-12.24048	-14.10044	-10.38051

For associating workers' gender in hand with job performance and job security, t-test was deployed for processing as in table 4.19 and 4.20. A significant variance of score between the two groups of gender does exist, $t(27.675) = -20.935$, $p < .05$, two-tailed with Male ($M = 9.1250$, $SD = 1.41761$) having different score with Female ($M = 20.9524$, $SD = 2.37647$). The level of variances in the mean (mean difference = -11.82738 , 95% CI: -12.98525 to -10.66951) was lesser (eta squared = .05). Hence, the null H_{04} can be rejected as workers' gender has significant difference of attitude towards job security. Similarly, the significance of variance of gender and job performance has a score of .012, the relevant scores of significance. (2-tailed) under t-test for equality of mean is (0.000) lesser than 0.05, indicating that, the H_{04} there is no association of workers' gender and job performance can be rejected as significant difference of score between the two groups of gender does exist with regard to job performance, $t(32.385) = -13.399$, $p < .05$, two-tailed with Male ($M = 12.9500$, $SD = 2.78227$) having different score with Female ($M = 25.1905$, $SD = 3.66905$). The level of variances in the mean (mean difference = -12.24048 , 95% CI: -14.10044 to -10.38051) was lesser (eta squared = .05). The facts of gender in association with job performance and job security are supported by Hakim, 1999, Jimoh, 2008 and Stone et al., 2016 as explained in the literature.

Table 4.21 Kruskal-Wallis test statistics

Kruskal-Wallis	Job performance			Job Security		
	df	Chi-square	Sig.	df	Chi-square	Sig.
Age	4	57.141	.000	4	58.396	.000

Kruskal-Wallis test was deployed to justify the existence of significant difference among workers' age levels with job performance and job security. Table 4.21 gives the significant difference of age on work performance as ($p = .000 < 0.05$) and that of age with job security as ($p = .000 < 0.05$). Thus, the null H_{04} is not accepted. The facts of the difference of workers' age levels in relation to job performance and job security are supported by Darwin, 2014 and Timar, 2014.

Table 4.22 Descriptives Statistics for job performance

Age Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
18-20	10	11.0000	.00000	11.00	11.00
21-30	16	11.3125	.47871	11.00	12.00
31-40	15	16.4667	2.41622	13.00	20.00
41-50	16	24.3125	2.98259	21.00	29.00
51	5	30.0000	1.00000	29.00	31.00
Total	62	17.3710	6.77080	11.00	31.00

Table 4.23 ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2573.859	4	643.465	164.762	.000
Within Groups	222.608	57	3.905		
Total	2796.468	61			

Table 4.22 has significant score of .000 small than the required alpha .05, thus, the null H_{04} is rejected because significant differences exist between age levels with Job Performance, $F(4, 57) = 164.762$, $p < .00$. Workers' Job performance differs significantly with their age levels.

5. Ending Remarks from the study

Working for unsatisfactory performance in public sector is vexing and costly in terms of time and other resources, despite the presence of job security in public sector as a determining factor of job performance, persisting performance problems are still there and are attributed by a number of factors like absence of

performance culture and low incentives as Bloom & Van Reenen (2011) insist that, workers should be rewarded for performance culture based, also, performance problems are not addressed properly and timely; some studies found workers with performance problems been shifted (Gallo, 2014) or managers hiding performance problems of their workers to higher authority for relations purposes (Guffey and Helms, 2001) which has been the case to. Bloom & Van Reenen, (2011) argued that, developing countries have the problem of embracing underperformers without punishing them. Inappropriate work behaviours like prioritising work time for gossiping, unhealthy work-life balance, inappropriate managerial practices accompanied by fear of making decisions or making decision basing on grapevine, personality misfit with jobs as well as between workers and leaders due to recruitment and selection problems. Line managers are found to have subjective assessment of workers' performance and consistent deleterious feedback from performance appraisal as Brown and Benson (2003) says, consistent negative feedback to your workers kills their work moral; also, overloading problems have resulted to poor output. All these problems account for public sector workers' negative attitudes towards public funds, properties, and performance problems.

5.1 Recommendations

Management should invest in building workers' positive attitude towards public interest for them to render excellent service. But also, line managers have to be objective in performance assessment, stop hiding performance problems and ought to offer constructive feedback to their workers.

To embark on regular trainings and development programs as well as yearly assessment of managers by workers and consultants from private sectors to share best managerial practices in matters related to performances like the use of Deming's 14 points and implementations of Kaizen techniques.

Hiring talented people is not the ultimate solution to performance problems; rather, management should work for best mechanisms that will raise and sustain performance culture. In hand with that, management should promote realistic and timely budget for regular performance incentives as current changes in management practices demands the working culture be reconsidered as an important ingredient of success by portraying new values and new working culture that is associated with new public sector management strategies and people with proper traits as Riordan (2015) says, performance culture in public sector is highly influenced by politics rather than market influence.

Work on reminding workers on the role of self-values, integrity and the sort of output expected from them, discourage gossiping acts and line-managers making decisions basing on grapevine as well as counselling workers on work-life balance and act in due diligent in protecting public properties and funds as workers have negative attitude towards these stuffs.

Breaking gaps between managers and workers to build good relationship between them, Tamkin et al., (2003) argue managers to employ good expertise to enhance work behaviour and stand for timely career development, studies insist management to account for proper development of its human capital to foster workers capabilities (Mutegi and Ombui, 2016).

Avoid hiring on self-interest. It has been a knocking problem in public sector giving room for siding top performers and attracting underperformers.

Avoid keeping management people whose tenure has lapsed in the same place as they bring difficulties for new managers to deal with their performance problem and they may also have due influence to new manager's decision and those who were his/her subordinates.

References

Abdullah, I., Rashid, Y., & Omar, R. (2013). Effect of Personality on Job Performance of Employees: Empirical Evidence from Banking Sector of Pakistan Middle-East. *Journal of Scientific Research*, 17 (12):1735-1741.

- Ahmed, W., Yasir, M., Nawaz, R., Imran, and Nawaz, A. (2016). A Mediating Role of Job Security between Trust and Employees' Performance: A Case of Private Sector Hospitals of Hazara Division, Pakistan. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management* Volume 18, Issue 9 .Ver. IV www.iosrjournals.org
- Albino, G. (2018). Technical and Behavioral Competencies on Performance Evaluation: Petrek Leaders' Perspectives. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/2158244018780972>
- Anwar, M. S., Aslam, M., and Tariq, M. R. (2011). Temporary Job and its Impact on Employee Performance. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research* Volume 11 Issue 8 Version 1.0. (USA)
- Armstrong, M. (2006). *Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*, 10th Edition, Published at Kogan Page Limited.
- Awadh, I. M., Gichinga, L and Ahmed, A. H. (2015). Effects of workplace stress on employee performance in the county governments in Kenya: A case study of kilifi county government. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 5, Issue 10,
- Baker, M. J. and Fouad A. I. (1993). Organizational buying behavior in the Gulf, *International Marketing Review*, 10(6), 42-60.
- Beardwell, I. and Nell, (2001). *Human Resources Contemporary Approach*, 4th Ed, Person Education Ltd, London
- Blackwell, D. R., Miniard W. P., Engel F. J. (2001). *Consumer Behavior*, 9th Ed, South Western-Thomson Learning. https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/45148/9/09_chapter%202.pdf
- Bloom, N., & Van Reenen, J. (2011). Human resource management and productivity. In: Ashenfelter, O., Card, D. (Eds.), *Handbook of Labor Economics* (pp. 1697–1767., vol.4b). Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Brown, M., Benson, J. (2003). Rated to exhaustion? Reaction to performance appraisal process. *Industrial relations journal*, Vol. 34;1.
- Cascio, W. F. (2006). *Managing Human Resources: Productivity, Quality of Life, Profits*.
- Cardy, R. L. (2004). *Performance management: Concepts, skills, and exercises*. M.E. Sharpe, Armonk, NY.
- Creswell, J. W. (2005). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Cronbach, L. J. (1951). Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. *Journal of Psychometrika*, 1951.3 (297-334): Vol. 16.
- Darwin, R. J. (2014). Age diversity and its impact on employee performance in Singapore. *International journal of research and development in technology and management science*. 211 (5), 79-98.
- Dexit, A. (2002). Incentives and organizations in the public sector. *Journal of Human Resources* XXXVII.
- Ezspss, (2020). <https://ezspss.com/test-for-normality-in-spss/>
- Field, A. P. (2005). *Discovering Statistics Using SPSS 2nd Ed*. London: Sage.
- Frese, M., and Sonnentag, S. (2002). Performance concepts and performance theory. In Sonnentag, Psychological management of individual performance. Ed. Chichester, UK: Wiley and Sons Ltd.
- Gallo, A. (2014). How to help an underperformer.
- García-Santillán, A., Moreno-García, E., Juan Carlos-Castro, J., Zamudio-Abdala, J. H., & Garduño-Trejo, J. (2012). Cognitive, Affective and Behavioral Components That Explain Attitude toward Statistics. *Journal of Mathematics Research*; Vol. 4, No. 5; 2012
- Gibson, J., Ivancevich, L., John, M. & Donnelly, J. H. (2000). *Organisations-Behaviour-Structure-Processes* 10th Ed. Boston. McGraw-Hill.
- Guffey, C., and Helms, M. (2001). Effective Employee Discipline: A case of the Internal Revenue Service, *Public Personnel Management*, Vol. 30, No. 1,
- Gupta, C. B. (2006). *Human Resource Management*, Sultan Chand & Sons, New Delhi K.K. Gupta for new age International Publication Ltd, India
- Gupta, A. S. (2016). A research paper on the Employees Attitude towards organizational Change. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*. Volume 15, Issue 2 Ver. XII (Feb. 2016), PP 44-47 www.iosrjournals.org
- Haenisch, J. P. (2012). Factors Affecting the Productivity of Government Workers. *SAGE Open* 1–7 DOI: 10.1177/2158244012441603 <http://sgo.sagepub.com>
- Hai Li, Baiyin Yang and Mian Zhang. (2011). Linking Organizational Culture with Performance: The Mediator and the Moderator, at SEBA-IE CASS - IEHAS Economics of Crisis, Education and Labor, Chinese - Hungarian International Conference.
- Hough, L. M., & Connelly, B. S. (2013). Personality measurement and use in industrial and organizational psychology. *APA handbook of testing and assessment in psychology, Vol. 1: Test theory and testing and assessment in industrial and organizational psychology* (pp. 501-531). Washington, DC, US: American Psychological Association.
- Huling, E. (2003). Rough Notes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 2 No. 1 pp. 17-24.
- Imran, R., Majeed, M. and Ayub, A. (2015). Impact of Organizational Justice, Job Security and Job satisfaction on Organizational Productivity. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, Vol. 3, No. 9,

- Jandaghi, G., Mokhles, A. and Bahrami, H. (2011). The impact of job security on employees' commitment and job satisfaction in Qom municipalities. *African Journal of Business Management* Vol.5 (16), pp. 6853-6858. <http://www.academicjournals.org/AJBM>
- Jimenez, H., and Didona, T. (2017). Perceived Job Security and its Effects on Job Performance: Unionized VS. Non-Unionized Organizations. *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention* 4(8): 3761-3767, 2017 DOI: 10.18535/ijsshi/v4i8.11
- Jimoh, A. M. (2008). Situational Judgment, Emotional Labor, Conscientiousness and Demographic factors as predictors of Job Performance among University Administrative Workers in Southwestern Nigeria. Thesis. Guidance and counseling, Education. University of Ibadan. X + 142.
- Kaiser, H. F. (1974). An index of factorial simplicity. *Psychometrika*, 39, 31036
- Khan, I., Dongping, H., and Ghauri, T. A. (2014). Impact of Attitude on Employees Performance: A Study of Textile Industry in Punjab, *Pakistan World Applied Sciences Journal* 30 (Innovation Challenges in Multidisciplinary Research & Practice): 191-197.
- Katzenbach, J., Steffen, I. and Kronley, C. (2012). Cultural change that sticks. *Havard Business Review*, July-August
- Khurshid, F., Qasmi, F. N. & Ashraf, N. (2012). The Relationship between Teachers' Self Efficacy and their Perceived Job Performance. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 3 (10), 204-223.
- Lekha, P. & Magesh, R. (2016). Difference between Employees Marital Status and Performance Level in IT Industry. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 2, 6.
- Longenecker, C. O., & Leffakis, Z. M. (2002). Serious about white-collar productivity. *Industrial Management*, 44(6), 26-34.
- Lucky, E. O. I., Minai, M. S., & Rahman, H. A. (2013). Impact of job security on the organizational performance in a multi-ethnic environment. *Research Journal of Business Management*, 7(1), 64-70.
- Moon, H. (2001). The Two Faces of Conscientiousness: Duty and Achievement striving in Escalation of Commitment Dilemmas. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 86 (3), 533- 540.
- Mutegi, M. F. and Ombui, K. (2016). An Investigation of the Factors that Cause Poor Performance of State Corporations in Kenya. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 6, Issue 11,
- Noraishah, D., Raja, P., and Pahat, B. (2017). Job Security and well-being among Private Workers in Malaysia. *Journal of Technology Management and Business*. Vol 04, No 01, 2017
- Nzuve, S. N. M. and Mwangi, P. N. (2015). Factors perceived to influence employees' performance: A case of the independent electoral and boundaries commission. *Problems of Management in the 21st Century Vol. 10, No. 2, 2015*
- Ojedokun, A. O. (2008). Perceived Job Insecurity, Job Satisfaction, Intention to Quit among Employees of Selected Banks in Nigeria. *African Journal for Psychological Study of Social Issues*, 11 (2), 204-220
- Omori, A. E., and Bassey, P. U. (2019). Demographic Characteristics and Workers' Performance in Public Service in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science* Volume III, Issue II, www.rsisinternational.org
- Ostertagora, E., Ostertag, O., and Kovac, J. (2017). Applied Mechanics and Mechatronics <https://www.scientific.net/AMM.611.115>
- Rao, P. Subba. (2010). Personnel and Human Resource Management, Himalaya Publishing House, Mumbai, pp.259
- Riordan, J. O. (2015). State of the public service series.
- Risher, H., and Wilder, W. (2018). What poor Workforce and Strategies is Costing Government. www.governing.com
- Sagepub, (2017). https://us.sagepub.com/sites/default/files/upm-assets/74890_book_item_74890.pdf
- Salladarr'e, F., Hlaimi, B., and Wolff, F. C. (2010). How important is security in the choice of employment? Evidence from European countries. <http://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-00526264>
- Şenol, F. (2014). The effect of Job Security on Perception of the internal Motivation means: A research from Turkey *Manas Journal of Social Studies* Vol.: 3 No: 1
- Sarantakos, S. (1998). *Social Research*. 2nd Ed, MacMillan Education Australia, South Melbourne.
- Shah, S. K. A., Ali, N., and Ali, Z. (2015). Declining Employee Performance in Public Sector Organizations: An Etiological Study of Public Sector Organizations in Pakistan. *Journal for Studies in Management and Planning*. Volume 01 Issue 05 <http://internationaljournalofresearch.org/index.php/JSMaP>
- Simon, M. (2001). Analysing and illustrating job attitudes of employees, managers and faculty members at domestic physical education universities and their relations to organizational atmosphere, Ph. D. thesis, Physical Education School, University of Tehran, Iran.
- St. Charles County Business Record. (2005, July 7). Human resource survey finds that poor management equals low productivity.

- Stone, T. H., Foster, J., Webster, B. D., Harrison, J. & Jawahar, I. M. (2016). Gender Differences in Supervisors' Multidimensional Performance Ratings: Large Sample Evidence. *Journal of Human Performance*, 29(5), 428-446.
- Sverke, M. and Hellgren, J. (2006). Exit voice and loyalty reaction to job Insecurity: Do Unionized and Non-unionized Employees Differ? *British Journal of Industrial Relations* 39, 167-182.
- Taber, K. S. (2018). The use of Cronbach's Alpha when developing and reporting Research Instruments in Science Education. *Res Sci Educ* 48, 1273-1296. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2>
- Tamkin, P., Hirsh, W., and Tyers, C. (2003). Chore to champions: the making of better people managers, IES Report 389
- Timar, D. B. (2014). The Dynamic Relationship between Aging and Job Performance – A case study. *Agora Psycho-pragmatica*, 8 (2), 75-89.
- Thomas, W. H. and Feldman, D. C. (2009). How broadly does education contribute to Job Performance? *Personnel Psychology Journal*, 62, 89-134.
- Vargha, A., & Delaney, H. D. (1998). The Kruskal-Wallis Test and Stochastic Homogeneity. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics*, 23(2), 170-192. <https://doi.org/10.3102/10769986023002170>.
- Walton, M. (1986). *The Deming management method*. New York, NY: Perigee.
- Yamane, T. (1973). *Statistics and Introduction Analysis*. 3rd ed. New York: Harper & Row.